

Diversifying tree species composition within Sitka spruce forests - implications for biodiversity.

A DiversiTree Research Note March 2025

Research summary

Tree species diversification of Sitka spruce forests is currently being considered to increase resilience both against climate change and pests and pathogens. Our research explored the implications of tree species diversification for the biodiversity hosted on Sitka spruce trees.

564 species were identified that use Sitka spruce across the UK. Most of the species that use Sitka spruce are common species that will use a range of other tree species. Not all the 564 species will be present on any one tree or in any one forest.

Diversification of Sitka spruce plantations with sessile or pedunculate oak, sycamore, Scots pine, silver or downy birch, beech, and Norway spruce will **provide the greatest biodiversity benefits**. These trees will not only support those species using Sitka spruce, but also support additional biodiversity not thought to be found on Sitka spruce.

Those tree species that bring the greatest biodiversity benefits will not grow in long-term intimately mixed stands with Sitka spruce because of shading.

We propose that **diversification of Sitka spruce plantations in 'blocky mixes'** - blocks of single species with tree diversity occurring within a management unit, rather than within a stand - is a pragmatic approach to **support timber production and provide biodiversity benefits**.

Further work is required to identify the **most suitable size and spatial pattern of these blocks** to meet the needs of production forestry, biodiversity, and landscape considerations.

Ultimately, **site-specific diversification strategies** need to be developed which take account of which tree species are most appropriate at a site level. This assessment should take account of the growing conditions (soil and climate), the risks of hosting tree diseases, and what local biodiversity is present that could be hosted by the proposed tree species mix.

Our research shows diversification of the UK's Sitka spruce plantations will provide both **greater resilience for the limited biodiversity associated with Sitka spruce and the potential for an overall increase in biodiversity**.

Background

Proactive management to increase tree species diversity within forests is frequently suggested as a way to increase resilience (Forestry Commission, 2023). With unpredictable biotic and abiotic risks, increasing the diversity of tree species spreads the risk load, since different trees are likely to have different vulnerabilities to pests and pathogens, drought, frost, wind and wildfire (Atkinson et al., 2022). Thus, if one tree declines, others may thrive.

For new plantations, recent guidance has stipulated that in order to receive grant funding “a diverse species composition should be maintained across the forest management unit so that no more than 65% of the area is allocated to a single species” (Forestry Commission, 2023). This provides an opportunity to diversify tree species, which in turn can not only help the resilience of timber supply and biodiversity but also potentially support additional biodiversity not currently supported.

Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis* (Bong.) Carr.) while not native to the UK, is the UK’s most economically valuable tree species (Forestry Commission, 2014). Sitka spruce (and all spruce species) are at risk from the invasive bark beetle *Ips typographus* (Evans, 2021), which has recently been found in southern England (Inward et al., 2024). It is also vulnerable to drought, which is predicted to increase (Forestry Commission, 2017).

The DiversiTree Project

[DiversiTree](#) is part of the [Future of UK Treescapes programme](#). It aimed to provide woodland managers with the knowledge and tools needed to help them to increase the resilience of their woodlands to climate change, and pests and diseases.

We wanted to:

- ❖ Produce a list of the biodiversity supported by Sitka spruce within the UK.
- ❖ Assess the potential of a range of other tree species to support the biodiversity found on Sitka spruce
- ❖ Explore what additional biodiversity might be supported by mixed plantings of Sitka spruce with other trees species.

This research note summarises our research results.

Our research methods are included as Appendix 1.

Sitka spruce plantations Craik

Results

The biodiversity supported by Sitka spruce in the UK

564 species were found to use Sitka spruce in the UK: 12 birds, 147 bryophytes, 28 fungi, 123 invertebrates, 243 lichens and 11 mammals (Table 1).

Six of the 564 species are only found on Sitka spruce but are all thought to be non-native. In addition, there was one lichen species that was obligate at the tree genera level in the UK (having only been recorded on spruce).

Not all 564 species will be found on any one Sitka spruce tree or in any one forest, in part due to the different distributions of these species within the UK but also because different species will use different ages of trees and different forest structures.

Forty-nine of the Sitka spruce-associated species have some form of conservation categorisation, typically indicating that either their populations are small or that their populations are declining. However, none of these species are highly dependent on Sitka spruce, indicating that Sitka spruce is not critical for their conservation.

Table 1. The number of species in different taxon groups associated with Sitka spruce

Level of association with Sitka spruce*	Taxon group						Total
	Bird	Bryophyte	Fungi	Invertebrate	Lichen	Mammal	
Obligate			5	1			6
Obligate genera					1		1
High			11	1			12
Partial	4	1	12	11			28
Partial genera				3	151		154
Cosmopolitan	6	41		31			78
Cosmopolitan genera		105		9	91		205
Uses	2			48		11	61
Uses genera				19			19
Total	12	147	28	123	243	11	564

*See Table 2 for definitions of levels of association

Sitka spruce at Clocaenog under planted with a mix of species for red squirrel

Other tree species that will support the biodiversity found on Sitka spruce

34 other trees were assessed as to whether they would support the biodiversity found on Sitka spruce (Table 3).

The native alternative trees that supported the greatest number of Sitka spruce-associated species are Scots pine, sessile and pedunculate oak, silver and downy birch, alder and beech (Figure 1). Norway spruce, European larch, sycamore, lodgepole pine, maritime pine, radiata pine, Japanese larch, and sweet chestnut were the non-native trees that supported the greatest number of Sitka spruce associated species.

However, the long-term suitability of these trees to grow with Sitka spruce needs to be considered. European and Japanese larch can form quite compatible mixture combinations that require some elements of planting design to ensure the mixture is viable (category 2, Figure 1). Scots pine, lodgepole pine, maritime pine, radiata pine, sweet chestnut are all amongst the most unsuitable trees for creating long-term robust intimate mixes with Sitka spruce (category 4), although they could be planted within the same management unit.

However, pines can be planted in intimate mixes in with Sitka spruce in the short-term, with the expectation that the pine will gradually be outcompeted, or that the stand will be felled on a short rotation before the pine is out competed.

The potential of the alternative tree species to support Sitka spruce-associated species differed between taxon groups. For the birds, Norway spruce, Scots pine, larch species, birch and alder appear to be good alternatives. Native tree species were generally the most suitable alternatives for the bryophytes, extending to the naturalized species of sycamore and sweet chestnut which were also good alternatives. We had low confidence about the suitability of many of the alternative trees to support the fungi, with the potential often classed at the genera level or as being rarely suitable. The non-native pines and spruces were the most suitable alternatives. Scots pine and Norway spruce best supported the invertebrate species. Scots pine, oak and birch were the most suitable trees to support the lichen species. Beech, Norway spruce and lodge pole pine were good alternatives for the mammals.

Tree species and their long-term suitability to grow in mixes with Sitka spruce

Figure 1. The number of Sitka spruce-associated species supported by other tree species that are suitable for growing in a mix with Sitka spruce. Long-term suitability for growing in robust mixes with Sitka ranked 1 (high) to 4 (lower) taken from Kerr et al. (2020) see Table 3 for further details. See Table 4 for definitions of levels of association

Additional biodiversity that could be supported by tree species diversification

Of the tree species most compatible with Sitka spruce that could, in theory, be planted as intimate, long-term, robust mixes (category 1, Fig. 2), sycamore would appear to bring the greatest additional biodiversity benefits. It would potentially support a further 646 species out of a total of 2822 assessed.

Of the trees classed as quite compatible with Sitka spruce (category 2, Fig. 2), birch and beech would bring the greatest biodiversity benefits, supporting 984 and 939 additional species, respectively. Also in the 'quite compatible' category is aspen, small leaved lime, Norway spruce and large leaved lime, with 540, 536, 536 and 480 additional species, respectively, out of 2822 assessed.

Mixtures including oak would bring by far the greatest biodiversity benefits – an additional 2187 species supported (Fig. 2). However, oak will only grow in mixtures with Sitka spruce if specific planting design features are followed (see Kerr et al., 2020 for further details).

Scots pine, and alder will support 1313, and 721 additional species, respectively, out of 2822 assessed, and maritime pine and lodgepole pine will support an additional 732 and 727 species out of 1363 species assess (category 3, Fig. 2). In the short term these species can grow in intimate mixtures with Sitka spruce, but their abundance will decline as the Sitka spruce ages and they are shaded out, unless thinning occurs to favour the alternative species. How quickly they are shaded out will depend on planting ratios and patterns and growth rates.

For long-term robust mixes with Sitka spruce, these pine species and alder would need to be planted within the same management unit but not in intimate mixes (Kerr et al., 2020).

Figure 2. The number of additional species not supported by Sitka spruce that could be supported by other tree species suitable for growing in a mix with Sitka spruce. Long-term suitability for growing in robust mixes with Sitka spruce ranked 1 (high) to 4 (lower) taken from Kerr et al. (2020) see Table 3 for further details. * = information from 2822 species available as to whether they will use this tree; ** = information from 1363 species available as to whether they will use this tree. Colours indicate different taxon groups. No = species for which we have information about their use of the tree, but we know they won't use that tree species.

Practical Implications & Recommendations

Our research shows diversification of the UK's Sitka spruce plantations will provide both greater resilience for the limited biodiversity associated with Sitka spruce and the potential for an overall increase in biodiversity.

Most of the trees that would provide the greatest biodiversity benefits, however, will not grow in long-term intimate mixed stands with Sitka spruce due to the shade cast by Sitka spruce and its fast growth rate (Kerr et al., 2020).

We propose that diversification in 'blocky mixes' - blocks of single species with tree diversity occurring within a management unit, rather than within an intimate mixed stand - may be an appropriate way to achieve species diversification of Sitka spruce plantations. This solution provides a pragmatic way forward that supports both timber production and biodiversity benefits.

The disadvantages of blocky mixes include:

- ❖ Wind throw, if one block is harvested or thinned before another.
- ❖ Visually, blocky mixes may not be as appealing as intimate species mixes.

The challenge is to identify the most suitable sized blocks and spatial pattern of these blocks that would meet both timber and biodiversity needs. From a production viewpoint, larger blocks may be considered optimal as they could be more cost-effective. From a biodiversity perspective, smaller blocks might be preferable. Bibby et al. (1989) showed that in non-native conifer plantations, there were more individual birds if broadleaved trees were dispersed throughout the conifers, rather than concentrated in fewer larger blocks.

The classification of the suitability of tree species to grow with Sitka spruce focusses on the long-term suitability, that is, mixes which will result in a long-term presence of both species on the site (Kerr et al. 2020). In the short-term, intimate mixtures of species with compatibility score 4 are possible and may bring some biodiversity benefits. However, these benefits will be transient if the alternative trees are shaded out after a couple of decades. In addition, older trees generally host more biodiversity due to the greater variety of micro-habitats they create.

This research note has focussed on the biodiversity implications of diversification of Sitka spruce. When considering tree species diversification, we should consider other factors such as the pests and pathogens that may be hosted by the tree species being considered for diversification. Currently larches are not considered a suitable species to plant in many areas due to the risk of *Phytophthora ramorum* (Jones and Wylder, 2012). Pine species are potentially at risk due to *Dothistroma* needle blight (*Dothistroma septosporum*) (Brown and Webber, 2008). Norway spruce is potentially at greater risk from *Ips typographus* and drought than Sitka spruce is (Evans, 2021).

Site specific strategies will need to identify which of the alternative tree species are most appropriate at a site level, both in terms of growing conditions, soils and climate, but also for hosting the local biodiversity as not all the biodiversity listed as Sitka-spruce associated-species or as "additional species" in this study will be present at any site.

Sitka spruce and Douglas fir mix at Clocaenog

Appendix 1: Research methods

We did an extensive search of published and grey literature and biological records data in 2023/24. The purpose of this investigation was to identify as comprehensively as possible those species that use Sitka spruce in the UK and the nature of this association.

The data collation was confined to species that use the tree (as a habitat space, or for feeding either directly eating part of the tree or for feeding on other species that use the tree). We did not include species that use the wider forest environment such as open glades or rides. Thus

data collation was confined to six taxon groups: birds, bryophytes, invertebrates, fungi, lichens and mammals. The level of association of each species with Sitka spruce within the UK was recorded as 'obligate', 'high', 'partial', 'cosmopolitan' or 'uses' (Table 2).

Information on the conservation status of associated species was recorded. We grouped these according to whether the species was known to have some form of conservation protection, as different taxon groups have different measures of conservation categorisation.

Table 2: Criteria used to assess the level of association of biodiversity with Sitka spruce in the UK. This includes species dependent on other species that use Sitka spruce, such as parasites and some of the predatory insects.

Association with Sitka spruce in UK	Definition
Obligate	Unknown from other tree species/cannot complete its life cycle without using Sitka spruce.
High	Rarely uses other tree species
Partial	Uses Sitka spruce more frequently than its availability
Cosmopolitan	Uses Sitka spruce as frequently or lower than availability
Uses	Uses Sitka spruce but the importance of Sitka spruce for this species is unknown
Obligate_genera	Unknown from tree species other than spruces/cannot complete its life cycle without using spruce but information not available about which spruce species is used.
High_genera	Rarely uses tree genera other than spruce but information not available about which spruce species is/are used.
Partial_genera	Uses spruce trees more frequently than their availability but information not available about which spruce species is/are used.
Cosmopolitan_genera	Uses spruce trees as frequently or lower than their availability but information not available about which spruce species is/are used.
Uses_genera	Uses spruce trees but the importance of the spruce for this species is unknown and information is not available about which spruce species is/are used.

Sitka spruce at Speymouth

Table 3. Tree species assessed for their potential to host the biodiversity supported by Sitka spruce. The suitability of the tree species to grow in long-term robust mixes with Sitka spruce is taken from Kerr et al. (2020) where 1 = most compatible with Sitka spruce and 4 = mixture combinations that are most incompatible. The Forest Development Types given are those where Sitka spruce is the primary species listed and the alternative tree assessed is listed as a secondary species (Haufe et al., 2021). Additional species assessment is the number of species which don't use Sitka spruce but for which an assessment is available as to whether they will or will not use that tree species.

English name*	Latin name	Native to UK	Suitability in mix with Sitka spruce	Forest Development Type with Sitka Spruce	Additional species assessment
Aspen	<i>Populus tremula</i>	Yes	2	1.1.8	2822
Beech	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	Yes	2	1.1.6	2822
Birch Silver or Downy	<i>Betula pendula/pubescens</i>	Yes	2	1.1.8	2822
Coast redwood	<i>Sequoia sempervirens</i>	No	1	1.1.5	1363
Common alder	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	Yes	4	1.1.7	2822
Douglas fir	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	No	1	1.1.3, 1.1.5	2822
European Larch	<i>Larix decidua</i>	No	2	1.1.4	2822
European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	No	2	1.1.5	1363
Giant redwood	<i>Sequoiadendron giganteum</i>	No	1	1.1.5	1363
Grand fir	<i>Abies grandis</i>	No	1	1.1.5	1363
Hornbeam	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	Yes	2	1.1.7	2822
Hybrid larch	<i>Larix x marschlinsii</i>	No	2	1.1.4	2822
Japanese larch	<i>Larix kaempferi</i>	No	2	1.1.4	2822
Japanese red cedar	<i>Cryptomeria japonica</i>	No	2	1.1.5	1363
Large leaved lime	<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	Yes	2	1.1.7	2822
Lawson's cypress	<i>Chamaecyparis lawsoniana</i>	No	3	1.1.5	1363
Leyland cypress	<i>Cuprocyparis leylandii</i>	No	1	1.1.5	1363
Lodgepole pine	<i>Pinus contorta</i>	No	4	1.1.4	1363
Lutz's spruce	<i>Picea x lutzii</i>	No	3		1363
Maritime pine	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	No	4	1.1.4	1363
Noble fir	<i>Abies procera</i>	No	3	1.1.5	1363
Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	No	2	1.1.5	2822
Oak (sessile/pedunculata)	<i>Quercus petraea/robur</i>	Yes	3	1.1.7	2822
Pacific silver fir	<i>Abies amabilis</i> Douglas	No	2	1.1.5	1363
Ponderosa pine	<i>Pinus ponderosa</i>	No	4	1.1.4	1363
Radiata pine	<i>Pinus radiata</i>	No	4	1.1.4	1363
Rowan	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	Yes	4	1.1.8	2822
Scots Pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Yes	4	1.1.4	2822
Small leaved lime	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	Yes	2	1.1.7	2822
Sweet chestnut	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	No	4	1.1.7	2822
Sycamore	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	No	1	1.1.7	2822
Western Hemlock	<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>	No	1	1.1.5	2822
Western red cedar	<i>Thuja plicata</i>	No	2	1.1.5	1363
Wild cherry	<i>Prunus avium</i>	Yes	2	1.1.7	2822

*The legislation with respect to which non-native tree species can be planted differs between the four countries within the UK. The inclusion of a species in this table does not imply that it can be legally planted and the relevant legislation should be checked.

Thirty-four tree species were assessed for their potential to support the Sitka spruce-associated species (Table 3). These trees were those recommended to grow in mixtures with Sitka spruce by Kerr et al. (2020), those listed as frequent in Table 5 of Stokes et al. (2023) as suitable alternatives to Sitka spruce and those listed as secondary species in Forest Development Types where Sitka spruce is a primary species (Haufe et al., 2021).

The level of use of the 34 alternative trees was categorised according to whether the species was known to use that tree, or just that genus of tree and if the species regularly used the tree or only rarely (Table 4).

The suitability of the 34 tree species to grow in long term, robust, mixes with Sitka spruce (Table 3) was based on their growth rate and shade tolerance and taken from Kerr et al. (2020). Kerr et al. (2020) ranked suitability from 1 to 4 where:

- 1 = most compatible with Sitka spruce and in theory could be planted as intimate mixes.
- 2 = quite compatible mixture combinations that require some element of planting design to ensure the mixture is robust.
- 3 = the mixture can be robust if specific planting design features are followed.
- 4 = mixture combinations that are most incompatible, species can be grown in the same management unit but not in intimate

mixes, a recommendation of a minimum area of 0.2ha per a species is given.

These suitability scores refer to long-term robust mixtures, that is, mixes which will result in a long-term presence of both species on the site. Intimate mixtures of species with compatibility score 4 are possible, but they will not persist in the long-term without management intervention due to the shading and growth rate of Sitka spruce.

In order to assess how mixes of Sitka spruce with other tree species could increase the biodiversity supported, we used the databases OakEcol (Mitchell et al., 2019b, Mitchell et al., 2019a) and Scots PineEcol (Mitchell et al., 2024). For 19 of the trees, assessed information on whether 2822 species that are not hosted by Sitka spruce would be hosted by these trees was available. For the remaining 15 trees information was available on whether 1363 species that are not hosted by Sitka spruce would be hosted by these 15 trees (Table 3).

We acknowledge this is not a complete assessment of the additional biodiversity supported by tree mixes, but it provides an approximation, given the limited data available.

Table 4. Definitions of criteria used to assess association of Sitka spruce-associated species with the 34 alternative tree species listed in Table 2.

Association	Definition
Yes_Sp	Known to use the alternative tree species.
Yes_Gen	Known to use the genera of the alternative tree species but no information on if it will use this species
Rarely_Sp	The associated species has been recorded on this tree species but very rarely, so unlikely to be a good alternative tree species
Rarely_Gen	The associated species has very occasionally been recorded on the genera of the alternative tree species but no information on if it will use this species. Unlikely to be a good alternative tree species
No	Not known to use this tree species
Parasite	Species is a parasite, so no assessment of alternative tree species made
Probable	Based on ecological knowledge of the species the associated species is thought likely or probable to use this tree species but there are no records of the species using this particular tree species. For example, the species is known to use a wide range of deciduous tree species, thus it is probable that it will also occur on other deciduous tree species, even if no records of its occurrence on this tree species exist.
Unknown	The use (or otherwise) of this tree is unknown

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Links to related research outputs for more detail

Mitchell, R.J.; Albon, S.D.; Bellamy, P.E.; Ellis, C.J.; Hodgetts, N.G.; Johnstone, C.; Stockan, J.A.; Taylor, A.F.S. (2024). Sitka spruce-associated biodiversity in the UK (Sitka spruce Ecol). NERC EDS Environmental Information Data Centre.
<https://doi.org/10.5285/1ce52c10-e3ab-4996-b9b7-052c70b3c1ba>

Mitchell R.J., Albon S.D., Bellamy P.E., Cameron C, Ellis CJ, Hodgetts N.G., Johnstone C., Stockan J.A., Taylor A.F.S.(submitted) Sprucing up the UK's Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis*) forests: Can tree species diversification benefit biodiversity? Forestry.

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